

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF ZIRCONIUM. PART II. CINNAMIC ACID

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Zirconium is shown to be precipitated quantitatively by cinnamic acid in 0.1N acid, HCl or HNO₃. The metal up to 0.6 mg. can be estimated and separated from thorium, manganese, uranium, cerite earths, beryllium, aluminium, nickel and iron with the reagent. Fe⁺⁺⁺ alone requires a second precipitation.

In an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 638) the use of cinnamic acid as a reagent for thorium was described. Further investigations have revealed certain useful characteristics of the reagent, which make it applicable to the estimation and separation of zirconium. Under suitable conditions, as little as 0.6 mg. of ZrO₂ can be estimated and 0.1 mg. gives a detectable precipitate. However, the precipitate is far less definite in its composition than the corresponding thorium salt, and ignition to the oxide is necessary.

EXPERIMENTAL

If cinnamic acid is added to zirconyl chloride or nitrate in 0.1 N- acid, there results a slimy precipitate which is difficult to filter and which does not wash well. When the two solutions are boiling, the precipitate exhibits better filtering properties. If ammonium nitrate is also added to the extent of 12 to 15 g./100 ml. of solution, the quality of the precipitate improves further: it is now curdy, settles quickly and washes well.

Reagents.—Two stock solutions of zirconyl chloride were prepared as described in Part I in this series (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 257) and were standardised by precipitation with mandelic acid; 20 ml. of solution A gave ZrO₂, 0.0433 g. and B, 0.0567 g.

Cinnamic acid of B. D. H. reagent grade was crystallised twice from boiling water.

Ammonium nitrate was of B. D. H. Analar quality. Other reagents were also of this quality.

Estimation of Zirconium

Procedure.—Aliquots of the zirconyl chloride solution were pipetted out into a 400 ml. beaker and diluted to 100 ml. Solid ammonium nitrate (15 g.) was then added and the liquid heated to boiling on a free flame. The flame was then turned down to maintain the liquid at incipient boiling. Cinnamic acid (0.4 g.) in 100 ml. of boiling water was added with continuous stirring. The flame was then gradually increased until the liquid began to boil. After 5 minutes of boiling the beaker was removed from the flame and set aside for about 5 minutes, when the zirconium precipitate settled as a curdy mass leaving a clear supernatant liquid. The precipitate was filtered hot through an 11 cm. Whatman No. 42 filter paper, washed with 3% ammonium nitrate, ignited wet and weighed as ZrO₂.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	ZrO ₂ taken.	ZrO ₂ found.	Diff.	Expt. No.	ZrO ₂ taken.	ZrO ₂ found.	Diff.
1	0.0567 g.	0.0566 g.	-0.1 mg.	5	0.0017 g.	0.0018 g.	+0.1 mg.
2	0.0433	0.0433	—	6	0.0011	0.0012	+0.1
3	0.0284	0.0283	-0.1	7	0.0009	0.0010	+0.1
4	0.0217	0.0216	-0.1	8	0.0006	0.0006	—

In experiments 7 and 8 the total volume of the solution was only 50 ml., the amount of the precipitant, 0.1 g. and of ammonium nitrate, 2 g.

Separation of Zirconium from other Elements

Thorium, iron and some other elements are precipitated by the reagent in neutral solution. Since the separation from these elements would rest on the control of p_H the maximum acid concentration at which zirconium would be completely precipitated was next studied. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Effect of p_H on the precipitation of zirconium.

Expt. No.	HCl in the final liquid.	Zirconium taken.	Zirconium found.	Diff.	Expt. No.	HCl in the final liquid.	Zirconium taken.	Zirconium found.	Diff.
1	0.0 N	0.0567 g.	0.0568 g.	+0.1 mg.	6	0.10 N	0.0433 g.	0.0433 g.	—
2	0.0	0.0433	0.0435	+0.2	7	0.11	0.0567	0.0565	-0.2 mg.
3	0.05	0.0567	0.0567	—	8	0.11	0.0433	0.0432	-0.1
4	0.05	0.0433	0.0434	+0.1	9	0.125	0.0567	0.0558	-0.9
5	0.10	0.0567	0.0566	-0.1	10	0.125	0.0433	0.0415	-0.8

Since the precipitation of zirconium is complete in 0.11N- hydrochloric acid, separations from a number of elements were carried out as follows.

To the mixed solution was added enough 2N- hydrochloric acid (usually 10 ml.) to give a concentration 0.1N in the final liquid. After precipitating zirconium as before and boiling for 10 minutes, it was allowed to settle for 5 minutes. The precipitate was filtered, washed first 3 or 4 times with 3% ammonium nitrate in 0.1N- hydrochloric acid and then with ammonium nitrate solution alone. The results are shown in Table III.

Among the elements shown in Table III, iron alone required a second precipitation for complete removal. This second precipitation was carried out as follows. The precipitate was only partially washed, dissolved in hot 1:1-hydrochloric acid along with the filter; the acid was next carefully neutralised with ammonia, acidified (to 0.1N) and the zirconium was reprecipitated as before.

Attempts to separate zirconium from titanium, vanadium, chromium and tin were not successful. In all these cases the presence of the foreign element not only delayed precipitation considerably but also led to incomplete precipitation. Thus separation from these elements appears not to be possible.

TABLE III

Expt. No.	Acid conc.	Element added.			ZrO ₂ found.	Diff.
1	0.10 N	Thorium chloride	ThO ₂	0.0522 g.	0.0431 g.	-0.2 mg.
2	"	"	"	0.1044	0.0432	-0.1
3	"	"	"	0.1566	0.0435	+0.2
4	"	Thorium nitrate	"	0.0681	0.0434	+0.1
5	"	"	"	0.1362	0.0435	+0.2
6	0.08 N	Thorium chloride	"	0.1566	0.0437	+0.4
7	"	Thorium nitrate	"	0.1362	0.0435	+0.2
8	0.10 N	Manganese chloride	MnO	0.18	0.0430	-0.3
9	"	Uranium nitrate	U ₃ O ₈	0.15	0.0431	-0.2
10	"	Cerite earths	R ₂ O ₃	0.42	0.0432	-0.1
11	"	Beryllium nitrate	BeO	0.21	0.0431	-0.2
12	"	Aluminium chloride	Al ₂ O ₃	0.23	0.0431	-0.2
13	"	Nickel chloride	NiO	0.24	0.0432	-0.1
14	"	Ferric chloride	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.36	0.0436	+0.3*
15	"	"	"	"	0.0433	-**

* The ZrO₂ residue is slightly coloured.

** Double precipitation.

Composition of the Precipitate

In order to obtain the pure compound for this purpose, the precipitate was finally washed with water. In this process, the precipitate became colloidal and significant quantities of zirconium passed through the filter. All the same, the residue on the filter was dried to a constant weight in an air-over at 105°. This dried residue on ignition gave a 1:1 ratio of zirconium : cinnamic acid. It is thus difficult to assign a definite formula and structure to the zirconium precipitate.